

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2

ISSUE 21 APRIL-JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“THE BOY WHO BROKE MY HEART”

You, the one I once admired,
the dream my restless heart desired;
the name I whispered through the night,
the arms I prayed would hold me tight.

You, the keeper of my heart,
the one I trusted from the start;
the man I thought my life would choose,
the future I was scared to lose.

You, the one who broke me down,
who left my smile without its crown;
the one who made my young heart cry,
the one who taught it how to die.

You, the boy I loved before,
who closed on me a painful door;
you stole the joy I used to show,
and made me small where all could know.

Yet still, your name remains the key
to what I lost and learned in me.

